

A Comparative Study of 0.5% Bupivacaine and 1% 2-Chloroprocaine for Spinal Anaesthesia in Minor Elective General Surgery

Swati Adivarekar¹, Gajanan Taktawale², Sandhya Gujar³¹Assistant Professor, Department of Anaesthesia, ESI-PGIMS, Andheri, Mumbai²Senior Resident, Department of Anaesthesia, ESI-PGIMS, Andheri, Mumbai³Professor & Head of Department of Anaesthesia, ESI-PGIMS, Andheri, Mumbai

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Swati Adivarekar

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Abstract:

Introduction: Various studies have been conducted to find a safe drug having early onset of action with short duration motor block for day care surgeries under spinal anaesthesia.**Aims and Objective:** To compare the efficacy of intrathecal 1% 2-Chloroprocaine with 0.5% Bupivacaine for minor elective general surgeries.**Method:** A prospective, randomized, double blind comparative study was conducted on 80 ASA grade I/II patients of either sex or age group 18-55 years, undergoing minor surgery under spinal anaesthesia.

The study population was divided into two groups of 40 patients each and were administered intrathecal block with either 1% 2-Chloroprocaine (2 ml) or 0.5% Bupivacaine (2 ml). The sensory block was assessed from caudal to cephalad direction with pin-prick test on each side, every minute until maximal spread of sensory blockade and then every 15 minutes during the surgery. Onset, total duration and mean time to achieve maximum sensory block were recorded. The degree of motor block was assessed using 'Modified Bromage Scale'. The onset and duration of the motor block were recorded. Mean arterial pressure, heart rate and oxygen saturation were recorded. Postoperative analgesia, duration of PACU stay and time of micturition were compared.

Results: The mean onset, duration, time to achieve maximum level of sensory block as well as motor block was significantly lower in the Chloroprocaine group over Bupivacaine group ($p < 0.05$), without any side effects.**Conclusion:** 1% 2-Chloroprocaine is the drug of choice for minor surgery under spinal anaesthesia due to rapid onset and early recovery of block.**Keywords:** Bupivacaine, Chloroprocaine, Spinal Anaesthesia, Minor Elective General Surgery.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Various studies were conducted to find a local anesthetic having faster onset of action and quick recovery from motor block, without any side effects [1,2,5]. Lidocaine fulfilled these requirements but was associated with transient neurological symptoms (TNSs) [3].

Hence, long-acting local anesthetics like hyperbaric Bupivacaine were tried in lower doses but showed delayed onset of action and recovery of motor functions [4]. In our study, we compared 1% 2-Chloroprocaine, pharmacologically similar to Lidocaine, with 0.5% Bupivacaine in patients undergoing minor general surgery in respect of onset and duration of sensory and motor block, hemodynamic stability, and time to return to micturition and side effects.

Method

It was a prospective, randomized, double blind comparative clinical study conducted over a period

of two years from 2017 to 2019 in the department of Anesthesiology in a tertiary care center in Maharashtra, India. The study was conducted after approval from the ethics committee and obtaining consent from the patient. The study was performed in accordance with the ethical principles specified in the Declaration of Helsinki and as per the guidelines of Good Clinical Practice. ASA grade I/II patients of either sex and age group 18-55 years, having body weight 40-80 kg, height more than 150 cm, posted for minor elective general surgery under spinal anesthesia, not requiring block above level T10 and lasting for the approximate duration not more than 2 hours were included in the study.

Sample size was calculated based on yearly turnover of the patients in our hospital, fitting in the inclusion criteria which was around 160. Considering a consent rate of 50%, sample size was calculated to be 80. Patients with deformities of the spine, infection at the site of needle insertion, raised intra-

cranial pressure, neurological deficit, coagulopathies or patients on anticoagulant therapy and having inadequate or failed block were excluded from the study.

Study population: 80 patients undergoing elective minor general surgery under spinal anesthesia, divided into two groups of 40 each.

- Group B: received 2 ml of injection 0.5% Bupivacaine intrathecally
- Group C: received 2 ml of 1% 2-Chloroprocaine intrathecally.

Thorough preanesthetic assessment (PAC) along with the necessary laboratory investigations of all the patients were done a day prior to the surgery. Patients were advised overnight fasting and the procedure was explained to them. They were premedicated with Tab. Ranitidine 150mg, and Tab. Alprazolam 0.5mg night before surgery.

In the preparation room, 18 G intravenous line was secured and preloading with an intravenous infusion of half liter of Ringer lactate solution was done. After the arrival of the patient in the operation theatre, all the standard monitors such as electrocardiography, non-invasive blood pressure and pulse oximetry were connected and baseline hemodynamic parameters were recorded. The study drug was prepared by the anesthesiologist not involved in the study and not disclosed to the anesthesiologist performing the intrathecal block and subsequent data recording. Under all aseptic precautions spinal anesthesia was performed with the patient in the sitting position using a standard 25-gauge Quincke's needle at the L3-L4 interspace in the midline approach. The study solution (2ml) was injected intrathecally after confirming clear and free flow of cerebrospinal fluid. Patient was placed supine immediately after injection.

The sensory block was assessed from caudal to cephalad direction with pin-prick test on each side. Patients were asked about the sensation every minute until maximal spread of sensory blockade and then every 15 minutes during the operation.

Onset time for the sensory block is defined as the time between injections of the drug to loss of sensation at L1 level. Time to readiness of surgery, Peak block height and Time to peak block height were all measured. Duration of the sensory block was measured from the time of intrathecal injection and recovery of sensation at the S2 dermatome.

The degree of motor block was assessed using 'Modified Bromage Scale'.

- Bromage 1 - subject is unable to lift his leg against gravity but able to flex his knee and ankle
- Bromage 2 - subject is unable to flex his hip and knee but able to flex his ankle.
- Bromage 3 - subject is unable to flex his hip, knee and ankle, but able to move his toes.
- Bromage 4 - Complete paralysis.

This was performed at 1 min, 3 min, 5 min, 10 min to assess the complete motor blockade time and then every 10 min after 1 hour to assess the time for return of normal motor function. The time between injection and complete block is considered as the onset time for motor block and that from the intrathecal injection to complete recovery of motor block is considered as the duration of the motor block.

Mean arterial pressure, Heart rate and percentage saturation of oxygen were recorded every 5 minutes for the first half an hour and then every 15 min, throughout the surgery. Patients were considered hypotensive when their systolic blood pressure decreased by one third from baseline and were treated initially with bolus of 250 ml of crystalloids and inj. Mephentermine 3 mg intravenously, dose titrated according to response, if needed. Heart rate of less than 60 beats per minute were treated with inj. Atropine 0.01 mg/kg intravenously.

Postoperative analgesia was assessed by the visual analogue scale (VAS), 0 was considered as minimal or no pain whereas 10 as the worst pain ever felt. Rescue analgesia was given in the form of intravenous infusion of injection Diclofenac. In the postoperative period patients were observed for side effects like nausea, vomiting, bradycardia, hypotension, hypoxia, transient neurological symptoms and urinary retention. Length of stay in the PACU and time of micturition were the discharge related criteria, compared in the two study groups.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed with the help of statistical software GraphPad InStat.v3.0. Quantitative data was presented with the help of Mean and Standard deviation and were compared by using unpaired t test. Descriptive statistics were used to note down the distribution of patients based on ASA grading and quality of analgesia. P value of less than 0.05 was statistically considered significant.

Results

The demographic details and ASA grading in both the groups were found to be comparable to each other ($p > 0.05$).

Table 1: Demographic Details and ASA grading in study groups

Parameters	Bupivacaine Group (n=40)	Chloroprocaine Group (n=40)	p Value
Demographic Details			
Mean Age (years)	40.3 ± 9.71	36.25 ± 10.6	0.19*
Number of Males	24	21	0.65†
Number of Females	16	19	
Mean Height (cm)	160.2 ± 7.9	162.85 ± 8.89	0.76*
Mean Weight (kg)	66.4 ± 6.94	64.95 ± 7.9	0.69*
ASA grading			
ASA Grade I	24	29	0.34†
ASA Grade II	16	11	

* Comparison by Unpaired t - test, p value not significant (p > 0.05), † Chi-square test indicates no significant difference (p > 0.05)

The mean onset time, the mean duration and the mean time to achieve maximal sensory as well as motor block were significantly lower in the Chloroprocaine group in comparison to the Bupivacaine group (p < 0.05).

Table 2: Sensory Block and Motor Block Parameters in study groups

Parameters	Bupivacaine Group (n=40)	Chloroprocaine Group (n=40)	p Value
Sensory block Parameters			
Mean Onset time (mins)	7.3 ± 1.28	1.82 ± 0.74	< 0.001
Mean duration (mins)	141.5 ± 22.53	54.87 ± 8.58	< 0.001
Mean time to achieve maximum level (mins)	17.1 ± 1.99	5.47 ± 0.84	< 0.001
Motor block Parameters			
Mean Onset time (mins)	11 ± 1.75	2.62 ± 0.66	< 0.001
Mean duration (mins)	124 ± 24.15	41.87 ± 11.41	< 0.001

p<0.05 considered significant by Unpaired t- test

There was a statistically significant difference between the MAP of Bupivacaine and Chloroprocaine group at all time points starting from 20 minutes and till 1 hour 45 minutes post-operatively, with significantly lower MAP in Bupivacaine group. (P < 0.05 by unpaired t test)

Figure 1: Mean Arterial Pressure (MAP) in study groups (mm Hg)

The mean HR was comparable in both the study groups at all time points except at 10 minutes assessment, when the mean HR was significantly lower in the Chloroprocaine group ($p < 0.05$ by unpaired t test).

Figure 2: Mean Heart Rate in study groups (per minute)

The mean post-operative time for recovery of the spinal level was significantly quicker in the Chloroprocaine group for all the levels ($p < 0.05$) and both the drugs provide adequate analgesia ($p > 0.05$)

Table 3: Mean post-operative time for recovery from Spinal Block (minutes) and Adequacy of Analgesia

Spinal Level	Bupivacaine Group (n=40)	Chloroprocaine Group (n=40)	p Value
T10	89 ± 19.59	30.72 ± 7.54	< 0.0001*
T12	102.5 ± 20.16	38.5 ± 8.02	< 0.0001*
L1	112 ± 21.51	44.47 ± 9.15	< 0.0001*
L4	119.5 ± 23.58	49.9 ± 8.42	< 0.0001*
S2	136.5 ± 24.4	55.37 ± 9.56	< 0.0001*
Adequate Analgesia			
Yes	32	31	0.99†
No	8	9	

* $p < 0.05$ considered significant by Unpaired t- test, † $p > 0.05$ considered not significant by Chi-square test

Table 4: Mean Length of PACU Stay and Mean time to Micturition in Study groups (minutes)

Parameters	Bupivacaine Group (n=40)	Chloroprocaine Group (n=40)	p Value
Mean Length of PACU stay (mins)	33 ± 7.91	13.37 ± 3.82	< 0.0001*
Mean time to Micturition (mins)	154.5 ± 21.41	77.75 ± 8.61	< 0.0001†

*value < 0.05 considered significant by Unpaired t- test, † p value < 0.05 considered significant by Unpaired t- test

Discussion

Spinal anesthesia is one of the most accepted technique due to the ease and high success rate [1,2].

The aim of this study was to compare the effectiveness of 1% 2-Chloroprocaine with 0.5% Bupivacaine in patients undergoing minor general surgery under spinal anesthesia, in respect of quick onset

and rapid recovery of sensory and motor blockade along with the hemodynamic stability, return of micturition and associated complications.

Selection of the right local anesthetic agent is the most important key factor in these patients to achieve early ambulation and discharge from the hospital with no postoperative complications. It was observed during our study that spinal anesthesia with 1% 2-Chloroprocaine can provide a satisfactory surgical block for short duration general surgeries, with early postoperative ambulation and return of micturition. In our study, both the groups were comparable with respect to demographic details and ASA grading ($p > 0.05$) (Table 1) which was in accordance with the various similar studies conducted earlier by Camponovo et al [7], Maes et al [8] and Teunken et al [9].

It was observed that mean onset of sensory block at L1 level, mean duration of sensory block and mean time to achieve maximum level of sensory block were significantly lesser among Chloroprocaine group (1.82 ± 0.74 , 54.87 ± 8.58 and 5.47 ± 0.84 minutes respectively) compared to Bupivacaine group (7.3 ± 1.28 , 141.5 ± 22.53 and 17.1 ± 1.99 minutes respectively) (Table 2). Results of our study were like that of by Yoos et al [6], Lacasse et al [10], Camponovo et al [7] and Teunken et al [9].

On assessing the motor block parameters by modified Bromage scale, the mean onset time for motor block as well as the mean duration of motor block were significantly lower in the Chloroprocaine group (2.62 ± 0.66 and 41.87 ± 11.41 minutes respectively) compared to Bupivacaine group (11 ± 1.75 and 124 ± 24.15 minutes respectively), exactly similar to that for sensory block (Table 2). Results of our study were in accordance with that of by Yoos et al [6], Lacasse et al [10], Camponovo et al [7], Maes et al [8] and Teunken et al [9]. All the patients in the Chloroprocaine group attained a score 0 within 1 hour 10 minutes of administration. This indicates that by 1 hour 10 minutes, the recovery in the Chloroprocaine group was 100%. For Bupivacaine, 24 of the 40 patients attained score 0 at 2 hours and 15 minutes, while the other 16 patients had still not completely recovered from the motor block. This also indicates that the motor recovery is delayed by Bupivacaine as compared to the Chloroprocaine group, where the motor block onset and recovery both are quicker.

The hemodynamic parameter recordings suggested that, Bupivacaine can cause more fluctuation in the BP as compared to Chloroprocaine. The mean MAP in the study was decreased significantly between 20 minutes and 1 hour 45 minutes of assessment in the Bupivacaine group with p value < 0.05 than that in the Chloroprocaine group (Figure 1). The mean HR was significantly different between the two groups only at 10 minutes, otherwise

the heart rate was well maintained and hardly fluctuated in both groups (figure 2). In the study by Lacasse et al [10], hypotension and bradycardia were comparable statistically in both Chloroprocaine and Bupivacaine groups. On the other hand, hypotension was reported significantly more in Bupivacaine group than that in the Chloroprocaine group in the studies conducted by Camponovo et al [7], Maes et al [8], and Teunken et al [9]. The number of patients who attained adequate analgesia was comparable in both the study groups, with the number being 32 out of 40 patients in the Bupivacaine group and 31 out of 40 in the Chloroprocaine group. The mean post-operative time for the spinal level was significantly quicker in the Chloroprocaine group for all the levels ($p < 0.05$) (Table 3). In the study by Lacasse et al [10]. Significantly more patients in Bupivacaine group acquired adequate analgesia as compared to the Chloroprocaine group (91% vs 81%). In the study by Teunken et al [9], the need for rescue analgesia postoperatively was lower in the Bupivacaine group. Hence, other related studies show that Bupivacaine may need lesser rescue analgesia post-operatively, however our study shows comparable need of rescue analgesia in both Bupivacaine and Chloroprocaine group.

The length of PACU stay in our study was significantly lower in Chloroprocaine group as compared to the Bupivacaine group (13.37 ± 3.82 vs 33 ± 7.91 minutes), indicating rapid discharge from PACU to general ward post-operatively. The time to micturition was also significantly lower in the Chloroprocaine group as compared to the Bupivacaine group (77.75 ± 8.61 vs 154.5 ± 21.41 minutes), indicating rapid return of ability to void the bladder with Chloroprocaine. (Table 4). In the study by Yoos et al [6], the mean time to ambulation and micturition was significantly quicker in the Chloroprocaine group as compared to the Bupivacaine group (113 ± 14 minutes vs 191 ± 32 minutes, $p < 0.05$). In the study by Lacasse et al [10], the length of stay in PACU was statistically comparable in the study groups (67 ± 16 minutes in Chloroprocaine group vs 68 ± 14 minutes in Bupivacaine group, $p > 0.05$). However, similar to our study, the mean time to micturition was significantly lower in the Chloroprocaine group (271 ± 96 minutes vs 338 ± 99 minutes, $p < 0.05$). In the study by Teunken et al [9], the mean ambulation time was significantly lower in the Chloroprocaine group as compared to Bupivacaine group ($p < 0.001$). Thus, the quick onset and rapid reversal of sensory and motor block by Chloroprocaine helps in quicker recovery of the patients without any side effects like nausea, vomiting, shivering, hypoxia and transient neurological symptoms (TNSs).

Conclusion

1% 2-Chloroprocaine is the drug of choice for minor surgery under spinal anesthesia over 0.5% Bupivacaine, due to rapid onset and early recovery of sensory as well as motor block with appreciable hemodynamic stability and without any side effects, leading to early discharge of the patient from hospital and making it economically more beneficial.

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